

DEVELOPMENT OF A TECHNOLOGY FOR OBTAINING DRY EXTRACT AND ESSENTIAL OIL FROM WORMWOOD HERB

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Relevance: Wormwood (*Artemisia* (spp.)) is widespread in the flora of Kazakhstan and has long been used in folk medicine as a medicinal plant for gastrointestinal diseases, as an anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and restorative. Currently, the demand for natural plant materials in the pharmaceutical, food, and cosmetic industries is growing.

Target: Development of a technology for obtaining dry extract and essential oil, rich in biologically active compounds, from the plant wormwood (*Artemisia* spp.), determination of their qualitative composition and substantiation of the possibility of their use in the pharmaceutical, food and cosmetic industries.

Research methods.

Methods of raw material preparation: Collection of wormwood herb and drying in the shade at a temperature of 40–45 °C. Grinding and fractionation (particle size 3–8 mm).

Methods for obtaining dry extract: Extraction; Maceration or percolation with 70% ethyl alcohol. Filtration: Vacuum filter. Concentration: Rotary evaporator under vacuum (≤ 50 °C). Drying: Spray or vacuum dryer.

Methods for obtaining essential oil: Hydrodistillation (Clevenger apparatus) or steam distillation. Essential oil is isolated and dried with sodium sulfate.

Physicochemical analysis methods: Organoleptic analysis (color, odor, taste, consistency). Determination of moisture, ash content, and yield. Determination of dry extract solubility.

Chemical analysis methods: HPLC – determination of flavonoids and lactones. GC-MS (GC - MS) – determination of essential oil content.

Methods for assessing biological activity: Determination of antioxidant activity (DPPH method). Study of antimicrobial activity (using antimicrobial test strains, agar diffusion method).

Results: A scientifically based technology for obtaining dry extract and essential oil from the herb of wormwood (*Artemisia*) is proposed. (spp.).

* Physicochemical parameters of dry extract (moisture, ash content, solubility) were determined and standardized.

* The chemical composition was analyzed and the main biologically active substances (flavonoids, sesquiterpene lactones, essential oil components) were characterized.

* The qualitative and quantitative composition of the essential oil was determined using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry.

* The yield of the obtained products is calculated.

* The antioxidant and antimicrobial activity of the extract and essential oil of wormwood has been experimentally proven.

* The production of natural products suitable for use in the pharmaceutical, food and cosmetic industries has been substantiated.

The use of local plant materials promotes import substitution and the development of domestic production.

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Conclusions: Dry extract and essential oil of wormwood are biologically active natural products. The developed technology allows for the effective use of local plant materials, import substitution, and the creation of new herbal remedies.